

Synthesis and complexation of some azo-sulphonamide derivatives

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Abstract : Sulphonamide-substituted benzimidazoles and their metal compounds were synthesized with the aim of determining their structures and biological activities. The synthesis was carried out by mixing sulphonamide and HCl below 10 °C and adding NaNO₂ to it to obtain the respective diazonium compound. This was added to a cold mixture of sodium acetate and 2-cyanomethyl-1H-benzimidazole in ethanol to obtain the required sulphonamide. Metal complexes are obtained by mixing metal acetates in aqueous solution. All the compounds were characterized by elemental analysis and electronic and IR spectral data. Biological activities were also determined.

Keywords : Azo-sulphonamide, synthesis, biological activity.

Sulphonamide derivatives were reported to furnish anti-bacterial, antifungal and anticancer properties¹. Also, benzimidazoles possess a wide variety of biological activities². Having the above facts in mind, we are interested to benzimidazoles derivatives containing sulphonamido moieties and their metal chelates in order to throw some light on their molecular structure to investigate their antimicrobial activities.

Experimental

All chemicals used are of pure grade. Azo-sulphonamides were prepared by dissolving (0.01 mol) of sulphonamide **1** in a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 5–10 °C in ice bath. To it a cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) was then added. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into a cold mixture of sodium acetate (3 g) and 2-cyanomethyl-1H-benzimidazole **2** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol to give **3**. The physical and analytical data are specified in Table 1. Metal complexes were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of the ligands with an aqueous solution of transition metal acetate in stoichiometric ratio (1 : 1 M/L) for 2 h. On cooling the complexes were separated, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. The complexes were chemically analysed and proved to be in a pure form. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was measured by Jouy method. Electronic spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer λ35

UV/Vis spectrometer. IR spectra were measured using Perkin-Elmer spectrum RX1FT-IR. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ at 200 MHz on a Varian Gemini NMR spectrometer (δ, ppm) using TMS as an internal standard. Molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMF solution using a Cole-Parmer 8500-05 conductivity meter.

The agar diffusion technique³ was used to measure the biological activity. The compounds were screened *in vitro* against four strains of bacteria : *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-6538-P), *Bacillus cereus* (NRRL-β-569), *Serratia macrescens* (IMRU-70), *Proteus mirabilis* (NCTC-289) and one strain of fungi : *Aspergillus fumigatus* (PP-29). A 1 mg/ml solution in DMF was used. The bacteria and fungi were maintained on nutrient agar and Gzapek's-Dox agar media, respectively. The agar media were incubated different microorganisms culture tested. After 24 h of incubation at 30 °C for bacteria and 48 h of incubation at 28 °C for fungi, the diameter of inhibition zone (mm) was measured (Table 4). Ampicillin in a concentration 25 μg mL⁻¹ and mycostatin 30 μg mL⁻¹ were used as references for antibacterial and antifungal activities. The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the tested compounds was measured by a two fold serial dilution method⁴.

Results and discussion

The novel azo-sulphanoamides **3a-c** were achieved by

Table 1. Physical and ¹H NMR spectral data of ligands and their metal chelates

Compd.	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Analysis (%) : Required (Found)				¹ H NMR (DMSO-d ₆) δ (ppm)		Λ _M mohs cm ² mol ⁻¹
				C	H	N	S	M	M	
3a	Yellow	290	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ S	52.94 (52.72)	3.52 (3.46)	24.70 (24.51)	9.41 (9.13)	-	-	-
3a ₁	Brown	<350	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ S Cu(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	40.93 (40.82)	3.94 (3.85)	15.08 (15.11)	5.74 (5.62)	11.31 (11.24)	11.9	11.9
3a ₂	Brown	<350	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ S Ni(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	41.25 (41.30)	3.98 (3.94)	15.19 (15.08)	5.78 (5.62)	10.62 (10.51)	10.2	10.2
3a ₃	Red	<350	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ S Co(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	41.23 (41.25)	3.97 (3.84)	15.19 (15.20)	5.78 (5.75)	10.65 (10.71)	10.1	10.1
3b	Yellow	300	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₈ S	54.54 (54.61)	3.34 (3.38)	26.79 (26.63)	7.65 (7.56)	-	6.99-7.98 (12H, m, 11H-Ar and SO ₂ NH), 8.49 (1H, s, NH), 12.40 (1H, hump, NH)	9.2
3b ₁	Brown	<350	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₈ S Cu(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	43.46 (43.32)	3.77 (3.72)	17.63 (17.51)	5.03 (5.10)	9.92 (9.81)	9.2	9.2
3b ₂	Brown	<350	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₈ S Ni(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	43.76 (43.62)	3.80 (3.72)	17.75 (17.64)	5.07 (5.15)	9.30 (9.25)	8.3	8.3
3b ₃	Reddish brown	<350	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₈ S Co(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	43.74 (43.71)	3.75 (3.62)	17.75 (17.69)	5.07 (5.11)	9.34 (9.41)	8.6	8.6
3c	Yellow	280	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₈ S	55.55 (55.51)	3.70 (3.63)	25.92 (25.81)	7.40 (7.51)	-	2.33 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.90-8.03 (11H, m, 10H-Ar and SO ₂ NH), 8.34 (1H, s, NH), 12.1 (1H, hump, NH)	9.3
3c ₁	Dark brown	<350	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₈ S Cu(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	44.37 (44.25)	4.00 (3.92)	17.25 (17.36)	4.93 (4.90)	9.70 (9.78)	9.3	9.3
3c ₂	Brown	<350	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₈ S Ni(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	44.67 (44.54)	4.03 (4.10)	17.37 (17.32)	4.96 (5.01)	9.10 (9.21)	9.6	9.6
3c ₃	Red	<350	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₈ S Co(Ac ₂).2H ₂ O	44.65 (44.61)	4.03 (4.10)	17.36 (17.42)	4.96 (5.00)	9.13 (9.15)	8.2	8.2

Table 2. The main IR absorption bands of ligands and their complexes

Assignment	3a	3a ₁	3a ₂	3a ₃	3b	3b ₁	3b ₂	3b ₃	3c	3c ₁	3c ₂	3c ₃
vOH + vNH	-	3275 sh 3243 br	3225 sh 3234 br	3300 sh 3247 br	-	3467 s, br	3441 s, br	3447 s, br	-	3483 s, br	3422 s, br	3422 s, br
vNH	3270 m	-	-	-	3291 s	-	-	-	32215	-	-	-
vC≡N	2219 m	2211 s	2217 s	2211 s	2222 s	2210 m	2213 m	2212 m	2223 s	2213 m	2214 m	2212 m
vC=O acetate	-	1624 m	1618 w	1624 w	-	1620 sh	1610 sh	1612 sh	-	1615 sh	1612 sh	1607 sh
δNH	1540 vs	1525 m	1546 s	1525 m	1540 vs	1559 m	1559 w	1559 vs	1542 m	1547 m	1560 w	1559 m
vC=O acetate	-	1462 vs	1466 vs	1466 vs	-	1457 vs	1450 vs	1456 vs	-	1466 vs	1458 vs	1457 vs
vN=N	1411 m	1400 m	1413 w	1401 w	1409 s	1420 vs	1421 vs	1420 vs	1410 s	1416 s	1419 vs	1420 vs
δCH ₃ acetate	-	1374 w	1372 w	1374 w	-	1374 w	1362 m	1358 w	1376 m ^a	1376 m ^a	1371 m ^a	1370 m ^a
vSO ₂ antisym.	1322 s	1312 vs	1309 vs	1312 s	1318 m	1312 m	1311 m	1309 m	1318 m	1313 s	1311 s	1309 m
vC-N	1266 vs	1246 vs	1250 vs	1262 vs	1273 s	1264 s	1261 vs	1261 vs	1268 vs	1254 vs	1258 vs	1261 vs
vSO ₂ sym.	1150 vs	1147 vs	1146 s	1147 s	1147 vs	1134 vs	1132 vs	1134 vs	1136 vs	1133 vs	1135 vs	1134 vs
ρ _w H ₂ O	-	846 sh	833 sh	839 sh	-	812 sh	843 sh	851 sh	-	831 sh	843 w	831 sh
ρ _t H ₂ O	-	545 w	582 m	587 sh	-	512 m	523 w	525 w	-	573 sh	580 sh	513 sh
M-O	-	480 sh	475 sh	475 w	-	468 sh	487 sh	498 sh	-	468 sh	465 sh	462 sh

vs : very strong, s : strong, m : medium, w : weak, br : broad, sh : shoulder.

^a The ligand and its complexes contain another CH₃.

1 and 3-a; R = H
 b; R = 2-Pyrimidinyl
 c; R = 2-(4-Methylpyrimidinyl)
 Scheme 1

treatment of 2-cyanomethyl-1H-benzimidazole 2 with diazotised sulphonamides 1a-c in ethanol containing sodium acetate at room temperature in good yields (Scheme 1). The corresponding copper (3a₁, 3b₁, 3c₁), nickel (3a₂, 3b₂, 3c₂) and cobalt (3a₃, 3b₃, 3c₃) chelates were synthesized in a 1 : 1 L/M ratio.

The characterization of ligands was carried out on the basis of analytical data ¹H NMR, IR and electronic spectra (Tables 1–3). The IR spectra of ligands 3a-c (Table 2) revealed characteristic bands due to NH, C≡N, N=N and SO₂ functional groups. ¹H NMR spectra of compounds 3b-c (Table 1) were recorded in deuterated dimethylsulphoxide exhibited signals at about δ 12.10 ppm attributed to the hydrazone NH function. The electronic spectra of ligands (Table 3) showed two absorption bands at about 21300 and 25200 cm⁻¹ due to hydrazone and azo forms respectively⁵, in agreement with conclusions from the IR and ¹H NMR measurements. Thus, one could suggest that the ligands 3a-c are mixtures of the azo and

Table 3. Electronic spectral data for ligands

Compd.	Electronic excitation of hydrazo		Electronic excitation of azo
	(cm ⁻¹)		
3a	21786		25380
3b	21321		25000
3c	21376		25252

Table 3a. Magnetic and electronic spectral data for Cu²⁺ complexes

Complex	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	² T _{2g} ← ² E _g (cm ⁻¹)	Dq (cm ⁻¹)
3a ₁	1.92	13623	1362
3b ₁	1.87	13458	1345
3c ₁	1.85	13440	1344

Table 3b. Magnetic and electronic spectral data for Ni²⁺ complexes

Complex	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	² T _{2g} ← ^v ₁ ³ A _{2g}	³ T _{1g} ← ^v ₂ ³ A _{2g}	³ T _{1g(p)} ← ^v ₃ ³ A _{2g}	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)
3a ₂	3.20	10172	16420	25000	1017	852
3b ₂	2.98	10111	16339	24330	1011	813
3c ₂	2.95	10131	16260	24096	1013	796

Table 3c. Magnetic and electronic spectral data for Co²⁺ complexes

Complex	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	⁴ A _{2g} ← ^v ₂ ⁴ T _{1g}	⁴ T _{1g(p)} ← ^v ₃ ⁴ T _{1g}	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)
3a ₃	4.80	17543	22831	974	943
3b ₃	4.75	16949	20000	941	956
3c ₃	4.73	16806	20804	933	960

Table 4. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds at different concentrations (MIC) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) and inhibition zones (mm)

Compd.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC-6538-P)		<i>Bacillus cereus</i> (NRRL-B-659)		<i>Serratia marcescens</i> (IMRU-70)		<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> (NCTC-289)		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> (PP-29)	
	Zone	MIC	Zone	MIC	Zone	MIC	Zone	MIC	Zone	MIC
3a	+++	175	++	125	++	125	++	175	++	250
3a ₁	++	125	++	250	++	175	++	175	++	175
3a ₂	+++	175	++	175	++	125	++	250	++	250
3a ₃	+++	125	+++	175	+++	175	+++	250	+++	150
3b	+++	75	+++	175	++	250	+++	175	+++	175
3b ₁	++	175	+++	175	+++	125	+++	250	++	250
3b ₂	+++	175	++	175	+++	175	+++	175	++	175
3b ₃	+++	75	+++	175	++	175	+++	75	+++	175
3c	++	250	+++	175	++	175	+++	175	++	175
3c ₁	+++	225	++	250	+++	250	++	250	++	250
3c ₂	++	250	+++	175	++	175	+++	175	++	175
3c ₃	+++	75	+++	75	+++	125	+++	125	+++	250
Ampicillin	+++	25	+++	25	+++	25	+++	25	+++	30
Mycostatin										

Diameter of the zone of inhibition.

+ : Less active (0.2-05 cm); ++ : moderate active (0.6-1.4 cm); +++ : highly active (1.4-2 cm); ++++ : very highly active (over 2 cm).

The solvent used was DMF.

Fig. 1. Proposed structure for metal complexes.

hydrazone tautomers.

The electrical conductance were carried out in DMF and the observed values are listed in Table 1. The observed values of Λ_M indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes⁶.

Comparison of the IR spectra of the ligands and their metal complexes indicates that the intensity of bending NH bands about 1540 cm^{-1} is reduced, while the intensity of the N=N bands at about 1400 cm^{-1} are increased in the spectra of these complexes. This implies that these chelates are mainly in the azo form. Such comparison reveals that C≡N and C=N bands are shifted to lower frequency in the spectra of all complexes except for $3a_1$ and $3a_3$ complexes. Also, in these complexes δNH and $\nu\text{N}=\text{N}$ bands are shifted to higher frequency, indicating that azo group does not participate in the complex formation. All of these arguments may be taken as evidence for coordination through C≡N and C=N sites.

Inspection of the IR spectra of $3a_1$ and $3a_3$ chelates indicates that $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, δNH and N=N bands are shifted to lower frequency upon complexation. Thus, one could suggest that the coordination sites are cyano and azo or amino groups.

The complexes show two absorption bands at about 1615 and 1460 cm^{-1} , assigned to asymmetric and symmetric $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ respectively and this shows a remarkable

shift from the reported values of the free acetate ion⁷. This suggests that the acetate ion is involved in complexation, and is consistent with the molar conductivity results.

The electronic spectra of the ligands and their complexes were recorded in DMF solution. The observed electronic transitions are listed in Table 3 with their assignments. The electronic spectra of the ligands and their complexes reveal that the hydrazone band at about 31300 cm^{-1} is greatly reduced and becomes a shoulder upon complexation. This implies that these complexes are mainly in the azo form, confirming the IR conclusions.

The spectra of Cu^{II} complexes reveal broad overlapped peaks at about 13500 cm^{-1} which indicate considerable degree of distortion. Such distortion can be assigned in terms of Jahn-Teller effect in octahedral complexes⁸. The spectra of Ni^{II} complexes showed well defined bands, can be attributed to spin-allowed transitions. The crystal field parameters $10Dq$ and B were calculated using equations⁸ $\nu_1 = 10Dq$; $\nu_3 = 12Dq + 15B$. The peak positions and crystal field parameters indicate that Ni complexes have octahedral structures. The spectra of Co^{II} complexes contain two peaks at about 17000 and 21000 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g(p)}$ respectively. The electronic spectral parameters $10Dq$ and B values were estimated using the relationships⁸ $\nu_2 = 10Dq$, $\nu_3 = 6Dq + 15B$.

The biological activities of the ligands and their chelates were studied using the agar diffusion technique³ and their MIC were measured using two fold serial dilution method⁴. Results of biological testing are shown in Table 4. The data showed that all the synthesised compounds exhibit remarkable effects against the Gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus*), Gram negative (*Serratia marcescens* and *Proteus merabitis*) bacteria and *Aspergillus fumigatus* fungi. The proposed structures of the complexes are shown in Fig. 1.

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